

SMARANDACHE'S SYNDROME

Is characterized by nose frequently bleeding under stress, fear, restlessness, tiredness, nervousness, prolonged unhappiness. This is the way the organism discharges, thus re-establishing the equilibrium, and it is fortunate because the hemorrhage is not interior which would cause death of patient.

The bleeding is cause by the nervous system, not by physical injury.